

HALAL TOURISM: A NEW WORLD FOR TOURISM SECTOR

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Abstract

Tourism recognizes the growing interest in Halal tourism from both the perspectives of industry and research. Halal tourism, often termed as Islamic tourism or Muslim friendly tourism, is a new concept in the tourism industry that opens up new and exciting opportunities for enhancing economic growth. This qualitative, exploratory study examines the idea of halal tourism as well as the elements that make up the sector. It offers samples of some of the most recent best practices from around the world. Also covered are the advantages and disadvantages of promoting and expanding Halal travel. Despite the rapid development of Halal tourism, it is still important to consider the reciprocal benefits of both Muslim and non-Muslim tourists to preserve the longevity of this sector. There has not yet been a report that goes into detail on this new type of tourism that involves so many diverse nations. It was hoped that this study would stimulate further research in this area and improve the inclusiveness of halal tourism around the world.

Keywords: Halal Tourism, Islamic tourism, Muslim friendly tourism, income, advantages and disadvantages, research, travel packages

Introduction

Muslim travelers are increasingly looking for destinations that accommodate their needs in terms of cuisine, attire, and rituals, which is evidently a rising market area. "Halal" implies lawful in accordance with Islamic teachings when translated from Arabic. Gambling, drinking, eating pork, and nudity are prohibited. Halal tourism is defined as the use of any object or action by Muslim travelers that complies with Islamic teachings and supports the practice of the religion. It is a result of the rise in Muslim travelers worldwide and the rapid development of the halal business. As a result, Islamic principles must serve as the foundation for the application of the halal concept in tourism, including its development and promotion. Travel agents, while designing travel packages for this, follow guidelines of halal.

With a burgeoning middle class and increasing disposable income, many countries – whether Muslim or not – are looking to attract these travelers. Malaysia, the United Arab Emirates, Indonesia and Turkey are among the leading Muslim destinations. Singapore, Thailand and the United Kingdom are among the top non-Islamic or OIC (Organization of the Islamic Conference) destinations.

Statistics

The Economist's article on Halal Business published on May 25, 2013: "It is not just manufactured halal products. Services such as halal holidays are booming, too. Crescent Tours, a London-based online travel specialist, books clients into hotels in Turkey that have separate swimming pools for men and women, no-alcohol policies and halal restaurants, and rents out private holiday villas with high walls", which was featured on **Forbes** offers Muslim-friendly hotels and advice about halal food options, Quran availability and more.

Halal tourism is also important because the Islamic world is home to many major tourist markets and locations. In addition, 11% of visitors from outside are Muslims, which has prompted non-Muslim nations to provide Halal tourism services in an effort to better position themselves to capture a portion of the \$200 billion Muslim travel industry. According to recent research, Muslim travelers spent 169 billion USD in 2016 and are expected to spend 283 billion USD by 2022. In order to improve the growth of the industry, it is crucial to comprehend and promote the sustainable element of halal tourism.

In 2019, halal tourism accounted for 13% of the global tourism industry's value. In 2020, global spending by Muslim tourists sums up to 192 billion dollars. This represents a 126 billion dollar increase over 2017.

Halal Tourism Market Snapshot (2022-2032)

Halal tourism is anticipated to grow at a CAGR of 4% throughout the anticipated period, solidifying its position in the worldwide industry. The market for halal travel is expected to generate US\$ 255.0 billion in sales in 2022 and US\$ 365.0 billion by the end of 2032. Because of the expanding population, which is disproportionately young, educated, and upwardly mobile, the halal tourist market is expanding at a faster rate. **Demand for halal tourism** is on the surge with efforts to expand and promote tourism in Uzbekistan and Saudi Arabia and resurrection of lost heritage sites. With a growth in the number of wealthy Muslims, halal tourism is becoming more and more popular. The market for halal travel, tourism, and hospitality services has also grown significantly. One of the tourism sectors with the fastest growth rates in the world is the worldwide halal tourism market. The ethical consumer trends and the shift

in Muslim customers' attitudes around the world are to blame for the most recent changes in the halal tourist business. A wide range of halal tourism market opportunities have emerged as a result of the recent tremendous adoption of halal tourism, which is currently emerging as a new phenomena in the global tourism sector.

Before, the halal tourism sector was primarily connected to the pilgrimages of Hajj and Umrah; now, it is now linked to many other tourist destinations, helping to shape market trends in the halal tourism sector. Due to the rise in the number of Muslim customers in the upper middle class and the rise in interconnectedness, which has made travel a way of life, the demand for halal tourism is projected to soar. The halal tourism sector is anticipated to become mainstream and grow into a vital component of the thriving global halal tourist sector, satisfying consumer demand.

A wide range of halal tourism market prospects have emerged as a result of the huge acceptability that halal travel has recently attained and is currently experiencing on a global scale. In recent years, the hotel and resort tourism industries have exploded worldwide in response to the needs of Muslim tourists who wish to take advantage of hospitality services while simultaneously adhering to their religious tenets and maintaining Islamic customs and culture. Over the course of the forecast period, the size of the halal tourism market is anticipated to increase as a result of this development driving halal tourism acceptance. Many nations, including Turkey, Egypt, and Malaysia, have already incorporated this adjustment into their tourism offers to include lodging and other facilities that are in compliance.

Prominent Regions in the Halal Tourism Market

Malaysia is one of the fastest growing countries in the global halal tourism industry sector, holding a sizeable **halal tourism market share**. Recently, this country was ranked among the top 10 halal-friendly tourism destinations in the world.

The Organization of Islamic Countries (OIC) members are the main forces driving the halal tourism market growth, which in turn contributes to the 35% market share of the APAC.

The fast-growing resident Muslim population in some of the non-Muslim majority regions including North America, Europe, India and China is expected to ring about numerous **halal tourism market trends** during the forecast period.

Where North America halal tourism is projected to hold 27% of the market share during the forecast period (2022-2032).

According to Crescent Rating (2019), while Muslim tourists in general would value locations and amenities that meet their needs for faith-based services, a combination of culture, demographics, financial constraints, and the intended use of the trip will produce distinctive Muslim travel. Subgroups with varying tastes, giving

these factors the chance to tailor service offerings to their individual profiles, presented in table 3, as follows:

Table 1: Muslim key traveller profile

<i>Key Traveller Profile</i>	<i>Preferences</i>
Purpose	Leisure; Ramadan; Business
Demographic	Millennials; Females; Families; Senior Citizens
Budget	Luxury; Average Budget; Low Budget
Culture	GCC; South East Asia; Western Europe

Source: *Global Muslim Travel Index 2019*

Recent research, presented in table 2, shows the current and growing interest in halal tourism, the level of satisfaction with the product on offer, values, characteristics of halal-friendly hotels, travelers’ behavioural intentions, factors that motivate them to travel, the identification of trends and opportunities, the quality of the services offered, and an analysis of the opinions of travelers on social media.

Table 2: Key Islamic consumption values

Source: *Rodrigo &Turnbull (2019), Adapted.*

Difference between Halal tourism and Islamic tourism

There is one thing about halal tourism and that is the difference between islamic tourism and halal tourism. Many believe that these are the same terms and type of tourism. The term ‘Islamic tourism’ is more appropriate. However, the place may not necessarily be located in a Muslim country or in religious locations. If all of the facilities, activities, goals, and activities are permitted in accordance with Islamic beliefs, the activity can be referred to as Halal tourism. The same holds true for tourists who are not Muslims. So long as the actions associated to his claim are actually

permitted in Islam, a non-Muslim tourist may claim that they partake in Halal food and visit Halal entertainment venues. But in order to categorize travel-related activities as "Islamic tourism," another very important factor must be taken into consideration: if the action is accompanied with the Niyyah or intention on the part of the traveler.

Conclusion

One of effective means of accessing the market is to make Halal food widely available in the destination initially which is considered the high priority for Muslim tourists. Furthermore, Muslim friendly hotels should be available in the destination or at least separated sections in hotels where no alcohol beverages, no pork, Halal food are provided. Finally, Muslim friendly airport is considered a starting point that could be

used in promotion tools to market the destination as Muslim friendly. Perhaps qualitative followed by quantitative research to develop Muslim friendly destination criteria is recommended.

For the purpose of future research, developing construct of Muslim friendly destination is needed.

This qualitative, exploratory study examines the idea of halal tourism as well as the elements that make up the sector. It offers samples of some of the most recent best practices from around the world. Also covered are the advantages and disadvantages of promoting and expanding Halal travel. Despite the rapid development of Halal tourism, it is still important to consider the reciprocal benefits of both Muslim and non-Muslim tourists to preserve the longevity of this sector. There has not yet been a report that goes into detail on this new type of tourism that involves so many diverse nations. It was hoped that this study would stimulate further research in this area and improve the inclusiveness of halal tourism around the world.

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